

ANALYSIS OF CORRUGATED PACKAGING PAPER AND IT'S COMPONENTS BY DSC THERMOGRAMS

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Abstract: *This paper studies the characteristics of corrugated packaging under the pyrolysis process using the Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). The release of the heat and marginal temperature peaks of the main components were on-line measured during the tests. In thermal analysis the pyrolysis of high cellulose content samples with double exotherm peaks at 220-310 °C and 315-530 °C. Exotherms and endotherms in the DSC analysis closely connected to the presence of cellulose in the NaOH treated cotton, Kraftliner basepaper and Testliner basepaper samples. Analysis of Kraftliner basepaper and NaOH treated cotton showed two main exotherm peaks at 320-530 °C and with the Testliner basepaper, 330-530 °C. The releasing behaviour of the high cellulose content samples, the NaOH treated cotton was investigated and compared with the basepaper's thermoanalytical results where it was observed that the decomposition of the cellulose had the coherence with its quantity in it and the results were correlated with various cellulose content basepaper samples, as well.*

Keywords: paper components, corrugated packaging, DSC

1 INTRODUCTION

Significant part of the paper and pulp industry is the production of various paper or paper-based packaging materials (Tsujiyama and Miyamori, 2000). One of the most commonly used packaging materials is the paperboard. To prepare a clear identification of various basepapers of the paperboards has an

essential part of the quality processes, shown by Yang et al (2006). Since the testing of the base-elements has been used mainly for mechanical tests, several deviations can occur. Mechanical methods, for example ECT (Edge Crush Test), CCT (Corrugated Crush Test), RCT (Ring Crush Test), FCT (Flat Crush Test), are based on statistical technique, but can not provide appropriate results in any condition, as reported by Raveendran 1995. In case of the classification of the different basepaper's quality the same problem can be determined under the mechanical testing (Pöhler et al., 2017). As the quality of the paper is mainly defined by the cellulose and recycled paper content. It is difficult to separate it at the same time with the currently used test methods and their accurate ulterior identification is impossible with tests which are based on statistical methods (Yang et al., 2006). However, knowing and measuring the behaviour of the components of paper with thermo-analytical methods, the various physical and chemical changes can be monitored (Raunio et al. 2020) (Böröcz et al., 2016). As for the component's nature, every organic materials behave in a specific way and produce measurable differences under thermal processes. These differences are influenced by also the quality and quantity of the organic materials, which can be compared with each other. As a result of the examinations using a Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) apparatus, the classification of the basepapers can be implemented. With the help of DSC test, base paper types can be classified into a simple and transparent way. It is shown by Raveendran (Raveendran, 1995) and Yang et al. (Yang et al., 2006).

As the pyrolysis is a complex process, the samples go through many of endotherm and exotherm reactions and its heatflow (mW) and temperature peaks (°C) can be influenced by many factors (Chen et al., 2006). Mainly these reaction factors are due to the components of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin (Soares et al., 1995, and Ball et al., 2004). The cellulose and hemicellulose are natural polymers, which are appropriate for DSC analysis. Knowledge of the pyrolysis characteristics of components is the basis, so it is important for the better understanding of the thermal conversion. Using DSC to analyze the formation characteristics of charring process from cellulose pyrolysis at various conditions, showed by heatflow value (mW) according to the different heating rates. The organic mixture was classified but under the heating process it was difficult to distinguish these components from the perspective of exotherm and endotherm reactions. However, comparison of the heatflow (mW) and temperature peaks (°C) can reveal main constituents with the respect to the stages of pyrolysis process (Mitchell et al., 1960). In this study the knowledge of the pyrolysis of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin from the literature with the heatflow (mW) and temperature peaks (°C) of the NaOH treated cotton and the basepapers in various quality. The objective of this study is to gain extensive understanding about pyrolysis of the main

components which can explain the differences of the results among the various basepapers, thus facilitate to establish a comprehensive and universal model to identify the quality of the basepapers.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2. 1 Sample

The NaOH treated cotton for this study as the constituent of the three main components (cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin) were obtained by the Material Laboratory of Óbuda University, Hungary. This sample was also in board form with the size of 210 x 297 mm. The NaOH treated cotton contained over 90% of α -cellulose because it was appropriate for showing the chemical properties as a representative and comparable component of cellulose during various pyrolysis processes in basepapers. Filler materials as Kaolin and CaCO_3 were also obtained by the Material Laboratory of Óbuda University. Furthermore, the Kraftliner and Testliner basepaper were brought from Dunapack Zrt. (Hungary, Budapest). Kraftliner had an almost total composition of cellulose-sulphat, and Testliner samples contained 30% recycled paper and 70% cellulose sulphate. All the samples as can be seen on Figure 1. separately were selected from separate production, the various samples quality was determined by manufacturer's specification.

Figure 1: Measured samples of the study: NaOH treated cotton (A); Kraftliner basepaper (B); Testliner basepaper (C); Kaolin (D); CaCO_3 (E)

2. 2 Experimental methods

The pyrolysis of the samples were performed by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (SETARAM DSC 131 EVO). Using a DSC apparatus provided information for the typify temperature peaks ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and heatflow values (mW) of the pyrolysis process, which can refer to the chemical characterisation changes for each component. To mitigate the deviation of heatflow (mW) values and temperature peaks ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) the sample weight was kept at low level and defined in milligramm (mg). According to the repetition tests 5-5 samples were prepared.

The samples were heated up to 550 °C with a constant heating rate 10 K/min and kept on the maximum heat temperature (°C) for 3 min. Purified nitrogen (99.9995%) had been used to provide a constant. inert atmosphere for the pyrolysis with a 120 ml/min flow rate. Using this carrier gas to remove the gaseous and condensable products, thus minimizing any secondary vapor-phase interactions (Yang et al 2006). The energy changes were monitored during the heating and temperature increasing, keeping and cooling period as (1) equation shows.

$$dH dt = C_p dT dt + f(T, t), \quad (1)$$

where:

- dH/dt is DSC heat flow signal;
- C_p is a sample heat capacity (heat specific x weight);
- dT/dt is the heating rate;
- f (T,t) is heat flow that function of time at an absolute temperature (kinetic).

The preparation of the test samples were taken place in 30 µl aluminium jars, the average net weight of the samples were between 8-20 mg. The weight was measured by precision mg weight measurement apparatus. In the DSC apparatus, there were reference and a sample jars filled also. A predefined test program performed the thermal process using nitrogen purge during examination. The heating process started from 30 °C and was heated up to 550 °C at a rate of 10K/min. During the test it was recorded temperature differentials between the sample and the reference jar and the program was analysed data based on exotherm and endotherm processes and recorded temperature peaks (°C) and heatflow values (mW) as well. Each samples was measured by 5 repetitions and their averages graphically presented.

3 RESULTS

3. 1 Chemical structure of the components

The chemical structure was detected by using the DSC through analyzing the temperature peaks (°C) and heatflow (mW) were related to each other. Mainly, the exothermic and endothermic temperature peaks (°C) were observed at the marginal peaks of the elementary constituent as cellulose. From the perspective of the examination, the cellulose is closely connected to the following processes: primary, secondary and tertiary pyrolysis.

Figure 2: NaOH treated cotton DSC curves

Figure 2 shows the NaOH treated cotton curves, with local minimum and maximum points where its inflection points as the part of the exotherm and endotherm processes can be seen. The degradations of cellulose began at 220 °C and had its end over 400 °C. The main pyrolysis process of cellulose took place between 315 °C and 400 °C. The cellulose consisted of a long polymer of glucose without branches, its structure was very strong, and the thermal stability of cellulose is also high. The primary pyrolysis reaction was caused by the C-C and C-O bonds rupture of cellulose. This pyrolysis reaction is produced higher heatflow values (mW) where the decomposition of the cellulose occurred. Regarding the high primer cellulose content samples were shown the decomposition of carbonil (C-O-C) and carboxyl (C=O) groups of cellulose and hemicellulose between 280 °C and 500 °C.

As shown on Figure 3. Kraftliner basepaper DSC curve reflects the degradation of the samples the DSC curves showed the energy consumption properties based on the heatflow (mW) and temperature (°C) correlation in the pyrolysis process. At lower than 200 °C, the DSC curves of all samples showed a similar tendency, the first endotherm reaction occurred at ~ 100 °C explained by the removal of moisture when the sample heated up. With the increased temperature further (> 200 °C) the DSC profile of high cellulose content samples showed an obvious and firm endothermic peaks at ~ 355 °C. On the

DSC curves two peaks were found at ~ 275 °C and 365 °C respectively, indicating that their reactions were exothermic.

Figure 3: Kraftliner basepaper DSC curve

Figure 4: Testliner basepaper DSC curve

Figure 5: Minerals (Kaolin-red and CaCO₃-green) DSC curves

In Table 1 NaOH treated cotton and other different quality of basepapers (kraftliner-high cellulose content paper; testliner-low cellulose content paper) average results are presented. To achieve a better understanding of each reaction type connected to pyrolysis process, where the inflection points of the curves have changed, there were a local minimum and a local maximum points showed and analysed. The local minimum and maximum points were shown and analysed by both temperature peaks (°C) and the associated heatflow (mW) values.

Table 1: DSC results of NaOH treated cotton, Kraftliner and Testliner basepaper samples

Reaction type	Endotherm		Exotherm		Endotherm		Exotherm		Endotherm		Exotherm	
	I. Local min.		VI. Local max.		III. Local min.		VI. Local max.		V. Local min.		VI. Local max.	
Sample	T _{min} (°C)	Hf (mW)	T _{max} (°C)	Hf (mW)	T _{min} (°C)	Hf (mW)	T _{max} (°C)	Hf (mW)	T _{min} (°C)	Hf (mW)	T _{max} (°C)	Hf (mW)
NaOH treated cotton	102.42	5.62	166.06	1.55	252.02	3.23	326.77	16.05	348.42	11.36	532.64	48.21
Kraftliner basepaper	106.52	2.47	177.27	0.58	211.91	0.78	323.05	7.9	349.4	7.92	532.26	15.53
Testliner basepaper	103.28	0.83	166.25	0.44	233.6	0.71	331.05	7.34	350.98	7.66	531.89	13.03

Here we have to mention that the NaOH treated cotton samples in Figure 2, had its great importance in the experiment due to the fact that it has over 90%

α -cellulose content, which is an essential comparative fund of the various basepaper samples as it was closely related to the mechanical and quality properties of the paper's content. As the table, showed the primary pyrolysis can be observed between 252,02 °C and 348,42 °C, the secondary pyrolysis is observed around ~348,42 °C and tertiary was at ~532,64 °C. After the secondary and tertiary pyrolysis further reactions were not observed due to the fact that charring process was ended. The occurred heatflow values for the primary pyrolysis was 16,05 mW and for the secondary pyrolysis was 48,21 mW. The Kraftliner basepaper primary pyrolysis appeared between 211,91 °C and 349,40 °C in Figure 4. The secondary pyrolysis was from 349,40 °C to 532,26 °C. The heatflow (mW) values were 7,90 mW and 15,53 mW. The Testliner basepaper in Figure 5. had a lower quality as Kraftliner. The primary pyrolysis measured between 232,39 °C and 331,05 °C. The secondary and tertiary pyrolysis was at 350,98 °C and 531,89 °C. The corresponding heatflow (mW) values of primary pyrolysis were 7,34 mW and 13,03 mW at the secondary-tertiary pyrolysis. The results have been confirmed by other researchs as according to S. F. Ibrahim et al (Ibrahim et al., 2011) and Tsujiyama and Miyamori in 2000.

Figure 6: Comparison of DSC curves for various samples

Through the comparison of the three pyrolysis processes some similar points of the different samples were compared in Figure 6. According to the minerals in Figure 5, there was no significant decomposition process which occurred during the heating period. Primary, secondary and tertiary reactions of the

cellulose were measured in both samples of kraftliner and testliner basepapers. The determinative level of primary, secondary and tertiary pyrolysis of the different samples were observed it depends on the ratio content of cellulose. Table 2 shows normalized values of pyrolysis as showed increasing tendency regarding the cellulose content decreasment. These values were observed at exotherm reactions. Based on the endotherm reactions due to the inhomogenous heat absorbatation properties of the cellulose the normalised values showed higher values. This results confirm the previous researches e.g. Yang et al. (Yang et al., 2007) that cellulose consisted of a long polymer of glucose without branches, its structure is very strong, and the thermal stability of cellulose is high, compared to other components like hemicellulose.

Table 2: Normalized values connected to each pyrolysis reaction with the segregation of local minimum (min.) and maximum (max.) points.

Samples	Local min. points	T (°C)	Heatflow (mW)		Local max. points	T (°C)	Heatflow (mW)	
			Value	Normalized Value			Value	Normalized Value
NaOH treated cotton	I.	102.4	3	-0.1	II.	166.1	0.5	0.1
	III.	252	0.9	0.3	IV.	326.8	8.5	0.6
	V.	348.4	9.6	0	VI.	532.6	32.4	0.3
Kraftliner basepaper	I.	106.5	1.7	0.1	II.	177.3	0.4	0.2
	III.	211.9	0.8	0.3	IV.	323.1	6.6	0.1
	V.	349.4	7.9	0.2	VI.	532.3	13.1	0.2
Testliner basepaper	I.	103.3	0.8	0.1	II.	166.2	0.3	0.1
	III.	233.6	0.7	0.1	IV.	331	6.1	0.1
	V.	351	7	0.1	VI.	531.9	13	0.1

The different contribution of the samples obtained from the results of pyrolysis decisive differences where the total charring process showed also differences after the test according to the cellulose content level. Based on the ratio of cellulose degradation, under the primary, secondary and tertiary pyrolysis it was measured avaragely higher heatflow (mw) values, connected to higher temperature (°C) at the peaks of the reactions. This result confirm other researcher's results, as it was written by soares et al. in 1995, consequently it is generally accepted that the endotherm processes during the test is mainly due to the depolymersiation of cellulose with formation of levoglucosan and its evaporation, whereas the exotherm is due to the char formation.

4 CONCLUSION

The pyrolysis characteristics of main constituents of basepapers, cellulose and minerals, and also kraftliner and testliner were investegated. The differences

of pyrolysis behavior among the main constituent ratio content of the samples were drawn from the test results. At lower temperature below 200 °C all samples were produced similar curves. There were a determinative endothermic reaction at ~ 100 °C which was the leaving process of moisture. The pyrolysis of cellulose by NaOH treated cotton samples had been degraded and mainly happened at between 250-540 °C. At the following temperature (<500 °C), the pyrolysis of cellulose involved exothermic peaks avaragely at 166,06 °C, 326,77 °C, 532,64 °C and endothermic at 102,42 °C, 252,02 °C, 348,42 °C. Over the temperature of 500 °C the situation of tendency had changed and it showed rather endothermic before the end of the experiment. The behaviour of the Kraftliner samples evolving from pyrolysis under the measurement were exothermic with the temperature peaks at 177,27 °C, 323,05 °C and 532,26 °C and endothermic at 106,52 °C, 211,91 °C and 349,4 °C. The type of Testliner basepaper samples were produced exothermic reactions at the temperature peaks of 166,25 °C, 331,05 °C and 531,89 °C and endothermic at 103,28 °C, 233,60 °C as well on 350,98 °C.

The heatflow (mW) of DSC test suggested that different chemical structures of the samples attribute to different values were realised through the marginal pyrolysis processes. The cellulose displayed 1,55 mW, 16,05 mW and 48,21 mW values under the exothermic reactions and to the endothermic were connected by 5,62 mW, 3,23 mW and 11,36 mW (Hf) values. Type of Kraftliner basepaper showed 0,58 mW, 7,9 mW and 15,53 mW at the exothermic and 2,47 mW, 0,78 mW and 7,92 mW in case of endothermic reactions. The Testliner basepaper samples were produced 0,44 mW, 7,34 mW and 13,03 mW values were connected to the exothermic reactions and 0,83 mW, 0,71 mW and 7,66 mW were recorded as endothermic. At the Kaolin and CaCO₃ were no significant experimental results were observed, consequently it has no special influenced effect on the result of the complex chemical systems. The heatflow values also can refer to the charring process of the samples. Those exothermic reactions which were monitored, showed that the change of the cellulose content ratio, the values were higher. This difference might be due to the inherent variance among the chemical structure of the main components (cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin), for example hemicellulose appeared more C-O contained organics compounds, while higher contents of OH and C-O was found with cellulose and more methoxyl -O-CH₃ with lignin.

The thermal analysis was convenient and repeatable with the samples in various condition and useful method for characterizing heterogeneous organic materials and it was investigated for identification of basepapers according to the behaviour of the main components of the paper.

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